

Cluster Program as a tool for promoting circular economy in construction

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Abstract

Collaborating between public departments and units, research institutes, universities and companies is necessary for implementing circular solutions in the construction sector. As a part of its ambitious environmental sustainability goals, the City of Helsinki founded the Circular Economy Cluster Program in 2021. To support the great demand for new information about circular economy in the construction sector, the Circular Economy Cluster Program serves as a development platform for testing and developing solutions that enable taking the circular leap.

The Cluster brings together actors from within the city and the construction industry, co-develops circular solutions and processes, carries out real-life experiments and studies, and offers an informal space for knowledge exchange. Experiments and pilots are conducted on both city-owned development platforms, e.g., demolition sites and public spaces, and on privately owned premises.

Key words

Circular economy, public-private partnership, innovation, experimentation

Introduction

The City of Helsinki aims to be one of the European forerunners in climate change mitigation and reach carbon neutrality by 2030 (City of Helsinki, 2021). Construction is identified as one of the key areas to help reach these goals in Helsinki's Roadmap for Circular and Sharing Economy (City of Helsinki, 2020). As the capital of Finland, Helsinki has, in fact, great potential for supply and demand to meet as it operates in the local construction ecosystem as a client, developer, and a constructor.

On the contrary to the linear economic model, circular economy aims to keep products and materials in use at their highest value (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2017). Yet, more practical experiences and know-how are still needed to achieve circular economy in the construction sector. The City of Helsinki Circular Economy Cluster Program (CE Cluster) was initiated in 2021 to help accelerate the transition.

The three-year-program is funded by the city with three million euros and brings together professionals to create innovative solutions, tools, processes, and business opportunities. With the city taking an active role as a facilitator, the CE Cluster serves as a tool for testing and developing solutions that enable taking the circular leap.

Focus on collaboration between the public and private sector

Situated in the Economic Development Department of Helsinki, the CE Cluster works closely with different departments within the city as well as with private organisations. The Cluster is joined by more than 100 members from the industry, i.e., construction and real estate stakeholders, material providers, architects, construction and infrastructure consultancies, recycling operators, digital solution providers, universities, and research institutes.

The diversity of the participants throughout the value chain enables creating an ecosystem required for solving bottlenecks and advancing circular economy in the local construction sector. Participation in the CE Cluster is flexible and based on the needs of its members and the city.

All activities are conducted in collaboration with various partners on a case-by-case basis: the CE Cluster finds synergies between actors and financially supports projects that boost circularity and the experimentation of new materials or processes. It also promotes peer learning by organising innovation challenges, events, and trainings (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The CE Cluster challenged concrete companies to innovate new uses for mineral wool waste. One of the winning products, Cubeco, is piloted in Helsinki during summer 2023. Each module uses 300 litres of mineral wool that would otherwise end up in the landfill.

Finding solutions through concrete actions

While the objective is a systemic change on a larger scale, the CE Cluster seeks concrete, replicable solutions with agile experiments that contribute to the circular transition. One of the main goals is to help real estate owners and developers better identify materials and products that could retain or even increase their value when extending their lifecycle.

Activities facilitated by the CE Cluster include e.g., mapping out resources with pre-demolition audits, developing a data platform for reused materials, testing methods for extracting buildings parts, developing new products of reused materials, and updating circular procurement criteria. To benefit the whole industry, results are shared openly with the ecosystem and brought back into the city's own development (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Aalto University's students designed warehouses of reused materials for Helsinki's outdoor sports facilities in the CE Cluster's Closing Loops architecture competition. The concept "Lippa" is further developed as a pilot project.

There are still many questions to be solved about the process, regulation and cost structure for reusing construction materials and components – and three years is probably not enough to ensure the uptake of circularity in construction. The CE Cluster, however, has already initiated the change by influencing the city's own circular processes while also supporting the business of private actors.

References

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3. Ellen MacArthur Foundation. (2017). *Cities in the circular economy: An initial exploration*. Retrieved from <https://ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/cities-in-the-circular-economy-an-initial-exploration>.
4. Figure 2. *Aalto University’s students designed warehouses of reused materials for Helsinki’s outdoor sports facilities in the CE Cluster’s Closing Loops architecture competition. The concept “Lippa” is further developed as a pilot project.* Image by Johanna Saarela, Aalto University.

